

The 2025 Romanian presidential elections in the Republic of Moldova: Voting behavior, public perception, and contextualization

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Abstract

This study provides a critical analysis of the 2025 Romanian presidential elections, focusing on their unfolding and public reflection within the Republic of Moldova. Interest in these elections grew significantly among Romanian citizens residing in Moldova. The May 2025 vote followed a prolonged and intricate electoral process that began in 2024 and concluded with the annulment of the second round in December of that year. Intense public debate, the sustained visibility of the issue on the national agenda due to its implications for the Republic of Moldova, and the controversial ascent of the nationalist-sovereigntist movement collectively contributed to a marked increase in voter turnout. This study aims to analyze the voting behavior of Romanian citizens residing in the Republic of Moldova during the 2025 presidential elections. It further seeks to explore the significance, public perception, and impact of these elections - both in terms of their influence on the electoral process and their implications for the Republic of Moldova's European trajectory.

Keywords

Romania; Republic of Moldova; elections; president; European Union

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Introduction

The complicated electoral process of 2024–2025 brought forth challenges and forms of expression that Romanian society had generally never encountered before. The complexity of the process intensified amid threats posed by hybrid warfare, the challenges stemming from the traditional political system's inability to adapt, and the global proliferation of sovereign nationalist ideologies. These dynamics were further exacerbated by the failure of major political parties, the ongoing succession of crises experienced by Romania, and the exploitation of IT vulnerabilities that enabled the dissemination of messages via social networks through methods considered illegal. The information space, especially the online one, has been invaded by false information, conspiracy theories, disinformation and manipulation. This influx has contributed to the fragmentation and polarization of society, frequently giving rise to antagonistic groups characterized by rigidity and a lack of flexibility.

The Romanian diaspora has also been affected by this phenomenon; moreover, it has frequently been a prime target for messages that developed and turned into conspiracy theories within digital echo chambers. The Romanians living in the Republic of Moldova - our primary research focus - have also been swept into these networks. To understand the electoral process involving this community, it is essential to consider the broader societal context and the specific challenges they face within the Moldovan society.

The objective of this study is to examine the voting behavior of Romanian citizens residing in the Republic of Moldova during the 2025 presidential elections and to investigate the significance, perception and influence that these elections have both on the electoral process and on the European path of the Moldovan state. To achieve this aim, we have set three specific objectives: To conduct a quantitative analysis of voter turnout and voting patterns in the Romanian presidential elections of May 2025 in the Republic of Moldova; to analyze perceptions and public discourse in the Republic of Moldova regarding the Romanian presidential elections; and to investigate the significance and influence that Moldovans associate with these elections for the European path of the Republic of Moldova.

Our analysis is based on two research hypotheses. (H1): Participation and voting preferences in the May 2025 Romanian presidential elections among citizens in the Republic of Moldova were shaped by both internal political realities and the broader geopolitical environment. The presidential elections and the referendum on constitutional change held in the Republic of Moldova in October 2024, along with the tense backdrop of the Ukrainian conflict and the country's status as an EU membership candidate, have heightened interest in the Romanian presidential election and shaped the voting behavior of Moldovan citizens holding Romanian citizenship. (H2): The significance, public discourse, and perceptions were shaped by political and geopolitical interests, reflecting the views promoted in the Moldovan media.

Our research is based on two research questions. First, was the Romanian electorate in the Republic of Moldova motivated to engage in the electoral process based on their interest in the special relationship between the Republic of Moldova and Romania? And, second: was the voting behavior of Romanians in the Republic of Moldova shaped by the internal social and political context, in conjunction with the geopolitical context?

The levels of analysis we propose are in line with the objectives we have set and the structure we are developing. Thus, the first level involves a theoretical and conceptual analysis derived from the study of specialized literature. Particular attention is paid to the societal reality and identity dynamics experienced by the Romanian community in the Republic of Moldova in the applied context of the ongoing debate on electoral transnationalism. The second analytical level focuses on the electoral

engagement of Romanian citizens residing in the Republic of Moldova, as evidenced by their voter turnout and the expression of political preferences during the Romanian presidential elections held in May 2025. The third level is dedicated to an evaluation of public perceptions associated with the Romanian presidential elections and the evolution of perceptions associated with the electoral process, regarding identity dynamics and the special relationship with Romania. The fourth level examines the significance of the Romanian presidential elections for the Republic of Moldova.

Identity dynamics and the phenomenon of electoral transnationalism: the case of Romanians in the Republic of Moldova

The Romanian presidential elections held in the Republic of Moldova throughout 2024 and in May 2025 were shaped by the broader context of realities in Romania, the ongoing war in Ukraine, the internal dynamics within the Republic of Moldova, as well as the country's process of rapprochement with the European Union and its evolving relationship with the Russian Federation.

Recently, these issues have become central to the electoral debates attracting widespread interest in the Republic of Moldova. Issues such as identity, closeness to Romania (viewed by part of the electorate as a unionist inclination), European integration, the war in Ukraine, and relations with the Russian Federation were among the key dilemmas confronting Moldovan society, reflected in the fragmentation of electoral preferences. Moldovans holding Romanian citizenship were part of this dynamic, and their vote in the Romanian presidential elections was shaped by this broader context, alongside Romania's own electoral agenda. Additionally, a considerable segment of society remains interested in upholding conservative-traditional values, a national agenda, and traditional family structures (Băluță and Tufiș, 2024), which are also part of Romania's electoral themes and debates.

The geopolitical challenges are very significant and complicated by the internal context. The Republic of Moldova must consider not only the aspirations of the population's majority but also the identity divides within society. The political implications of this reality are considerable, having been shaped by Russian interference and influence over certain political parties, elements of the Orthodox Church within the Republic of Moldova, as well as by the direct and indirect control exerted over a substantial portion of the media throughout recent decades (Petrița and Țepelea, 2022). The Republic of Moldova has clearly and categorically expressed its pro-European orientation by requesting the opening of negotiations for accession to the European Union. Along with Ukraine, it was granted candidate country status, and on June 25, 2024, the first intergovernmental conference within the accession negotiations was officially opened for both countries (European Council, 2024).

The geopolitical landscape and internal political dynamics in the Republic of Moldova have been profoundly impacted by Russia's invasion of Ukraine in February 2022. The war has severely affected Moldova, economically, socially, and in terms of national and societal security. Russia's hybrid war against this vulnerable state is undermining democratic institutions and jeopardizing efforts to strengthen the rule of law and maintain political stability. The Transnistrian region and the Gagauzian Autonomous Territorial Unit are being used by Russia to generate instability and block the initiatives of the Chisinau authorities related to the European integration process. The frozen war in the Transnistrian region, in the context of events in Ukraine, has repeatedly shown signs that it could be reactivated. Political leaders in the Gagauzian Autonomous Territorial Unit have openly expressed support for Putin's regime and its policies toward the Republic of Moldova, including through official visits to Moscow, while actively opposing Moldova's path toward European integration.

Contextualization therefore plays an essential role in this analytical approach to the electoral behavior of Romanians in the Republic of Moldova. Understanding this context is also linked to the

numerous identity dilemmas and geopolitical antagonisms between East and West, which have created deep cleavages along identity borders in the decades since independence. Identity communities have always reacted electorally, but also geopolitically.

The context outlined above is exemplified by several cases. One such case involves Russian-speaking Moldovan citizens, particularly the Gagauz people, who have consistently favored aligning the state with the Russian Federation. A telling illustration is the referendum held on 20 October 2024 regarding Moldova's accession to the European Union. Citizens were asked to answer the following question: *Do you support amending the Constitution to enable the Republic of Moldova's accession to the European Union?* Only 31.02% of citizens from the Transnistrian region answered "YES." Thus, 68.98% of Transnistrian residents who went to the polls voted against the Republic of Moldova's accession to the European Union. At the same time, only 5.16% of citizens from the Gagauzian Autonomous Territorial Unit answered "YES." Therefore, nearly 95% of Gagauz voters who participated in the referendum voted against Moldova's accession to the European Union (CEC RM, 2025).

A key element of this context concerns the presence and characteristics of identity cleavages, where identity fragmentation contributes to a division of the vote along identity-based lines, including through the alignment of different forms of identity expression.

In the Republic of Moldova, as in other countries of the former Soviet Union, the post-communist period has been marked by a process of national-ethnic and national-civic identity construction, which has encountered resistance shaped by distinct identity-based particularities (Brie and Solcan, 2025: 159). This resistance has been expressed in various identity cleavages, which we have called identity frontiers (Brie and Horga, 2014: 202-216), as well as tensions or even identity conflicts. These may range from ordinary differences of opinion within society, including civil society, to more profound identity-based conflicts, whether inter-ethnic, inter-religious, or between distinct linguistic communities. The role of civil society (Brie and Putină, 2023; Costea and Brie, 2025), as well as European conflict management and negotiation instruments, proved useful in this process of mediating identity disputes and conflicts (Brie and Solcan, 2025: 159). In this regard, important steps have been taken towards resolving identity conflicts in the Western Balkans (Brie, Jusufi and Polgar, 2022; Brie, Jusufi and Polgar, 2023). Despite shared traits and challenges, the former Soviet space has demonstrated distinct approaches to managing identity tensions and conflicts (Brie, Costea and Petrilă, 2023; Brie, 2017). Distinctive features include the articulation of identity-based cleavages and boundaries (Brie, 2016; Brie, 2021; Brie, 2023), the role played by civil society (Polgar, 2023; Brie and Putin, 2023), the involvement of civil society in the democratization process (Putin and Brie, 2023; Poiană and Petrilă, 2023) and the need to stimulate cooperation (Brie, Mărcuț and Polgar, 2022).

Similar to several newly formed Balkan states, Moldova adopted a distinct policy during its first decade of independence that emphasized the unitary relationship between the state, nation and citizenship (Džankić, 2015). Moldovanism was developed as an identity construct with a role to serve political and geopolitical interests against a backdrop of numerous polemics and controversies. The controversy remains unresolved even domestically, without yet broadening the debate to other geographical areas whose geopolitical interests do not converge towards the same objectives. The debate between Moldovenism and Romanianism has often inflamed passions east of the Prut River, fueled to a greater or lesser extent by the West and the East (Brie and Solcan, 2025: 161). Without going into this identity dispute, we should point out that it had a significant impact on the electoral process, with identity issues often at the forefront of electoral debates.

Studies on transnationalism among immigrants have significantly influenced how the role of migrants in relation to states is understood, leading to new interpretations (Basch, Glick Schiller and

Blanc Szanton, 1994). Firstly, the links between the individual and the nation state are being reconsidered, as they are not exclusive but multiple in nature, thus calling into question the assimilationist theory of migration. Therefore, migrants involved in transnational activities can simultaneously develop social, religious, cultural, political and economic ties in several countries, including the host state and the state of origin. Secondly, the spaces where migrants engage in work, social, political, and religious life, as well as their everyday activities, cannot be neatly separated between their countries of origin and the countries of destination. They become, as Faist has pointed out, "combinations of social and symbolic ties, positions in networks and organizations that can be found in at least two geographically and internationally distinct places" (Faist, 1998:8). Transnational spaces are dynamic entities that evolve over time (Lafleur, 2005; Lafleur, 2013).

According to Benedict Anderson, "nations are imaginary political communities": "imaginary", because we can never know the extent of the nation as a cross-border phenomenon, "political", because of the community's membership to a particular state, and "communities", because this word best expresses the essence of the meaning of "we" (we, as the representatives of a nation) (Anderson, 1991). In the same context, it is interesting to analyze the concept of "travelling cultures", theorized by James Clifford (1994): "diasporas are positioned somewhere between 'nation-states' and 'travelling cultures', which implies that physically, members of diasporic communities reside within the host state, yet their astral and spiritual journeys extend beyond the geo-temporal and political boundaries of the nation-state" (Putină, 2016).

Some scholars highlight an additional value of diaspora studies: they propose an alternative paradigm to the concept of national identification. Prior to the emergence of this field, diasporic individuals were often viewed as mere fragments or remnants of the true citizens of their country of origin. Since 1990, however, theories of diaspora have offered alternative approaches that seek to no longer analyze "diaspora" as a term hierarchically subordinate to "nation" (Șerban-Opreșcu, 2010: 278; Putin, 2016). As part of the population living outside its historical homeland, the diaspora is involved, to one degree or another, in the internal affairs of the host society, thus becoming a political instrument at the transnational level. New research in the field of political science has focused on the impact of diasporas on the political process in their countries of origin (Putină, 2016).

Researchers place considerable emphasis on the political involvement of diasporas, identifying a wide spectrum of political action ranging from conventional forms, such as voting, joining political parties or advisory councils, to unconventional forms, including protests, boycotts, and civil disobedience. The degree of involvement can be stimulated by factors such as the electoral regulatory framework, the institutional openness of the country of origin, the logistical possibilities for remote voting, but also by the migrant's loyalty and identity link with the country of origin (Lafleur, 2013; Østergaard-Nielsen, 2003). States that have recognized the diaspora as an active political stakeholder by adopting various representative instruments (parliamentary quotas, dedicated ministries, recruitment of candidates from the diaspora or laws favorable to external voting) have succeeded in creating bridges of cooperation and mutual influence (Bauböck, 2005; Putină, 2017; Putin, 2018).

In this context, the political participation of Romanian citizens in the Republic of Moldova is part of an emerging paradigm of multiple citizenship and transnational influence, in which voting is more than a civic right – it becomes a vector of identity, geopolitics and democratic legitimacy. A frequently used argument in justifying the extension of voting rights to citizens outside the country's borders stems from the intention of states to maintain or strengthen political relations with citizens in the diaspora (Bauböck, 2005). The contribution of diasporas to the development of their homeland

extends beyond socio-economic dimensions, assuming political significance as their voices carry considerable weight in shaping the political course and election results in the country of origin.

The participation of Romanian citizens living in the Republic of Moldova in Romanian elections represents a notable example of transnational diaspora involvement, intertwining identity, geopolitical, and institutional factors. Romania has been among the countries that, since the 2000s, have actively encouraged voting in the diaspora, consolidating a favorable legal framework for external voting and creating conditions for the extension of citizenship (Waterbury, 2010).

The rise in voter turnout among Romanians in the Republic of Moldova stems from two key factors: the extension of Romanian citizenship to residents on the right bank of the Prut River, and increased awareness of Romania's expanding geopolitical influence amid the war in Ukraine and Russian pressure. This trend is further reinforced by the symbolic legitimacy of the Romania–Moldova partnership in the European accession process. Alongside its geopolitical and civilizational dimensions (Lafleur, 2013), identity is also coming to the fore. Thus, the rise in voter turnout among Romanian citizens in the Republic of Moldova reflects the symbolic cohesion between the two regions and expresses the emotional and identity-driven connection of the so-called "Bessarabian Romanians" to Romania. This increased involvement demonstrates the Romanian state's institutional commitment and its ability to project and extend sovereignty beyond its national borders. At the same time, it is important to consider the role of politicians in the Republic of Moldova, who use the topic of Romanian elections to assert their ideological stance and shape the public agenda, portraying Romania either as a strategic ally or as a symbol within a politically divisive identity project.

Figure 1. Assumption of ethnic identity in the Republic of Moldova.

Source: authors' elaboration based on census data provided by BNSRM (2025a and 2025b)

An additional factor behind the increased voter turnout among Romanians in the Republic of Moldova is the growing and more explicit embrace of Romanian identity, a process that has unfolded

alongside the rising number of Moldovans obtaining Romanian citizenship. The assumption of Romanian identity is also a cause (or perhaps a consequence) of the consolidation of a significant segment within the Republic of Moldova's population that supports the state's pro-European orientation.

Most of the population identifies as ethnic Moldovan-Romanian (82.1%). The self-identified Romanian community has grown since the country gained independence (from 0.06% in 1989 – 2,477 people, to 2.17% in 2004 – 73,276 people, reaching 7.0% in 2014 - 192,800 people (BNSRM, 2025a), and 7.9% in 2024 (BNSRM, 2025b). Meanwhile, the proportion of Russian and Ukrainian communities within the total population has decreased. The share of Ukrainians fell from 13.85% in 1989 to just over 6.5% in 2014 and 4.9% in 2024. The phenomenon is similar in the case of the Russian community: from 12.97% (1989) to 4.06% (2014) and 3.2% in 2024 (BNSRM, 2025a and BNSRM, 2025b).

In terms of linguistic identity, censuses in the Republic of Moldova have revealed several trends. First, a decline in the share of individuals declaring Russian as their mother tongue, although a substantial portion of the non-Russian population continues to choose Russian as their primary language: 14.1% choose Russian, while only 4.06% also choose Russian ethnicity). Second, the consolidation of the Moldovan-Romanian linguistic group, which rose from 75.2% (2004) to 76.3% (2014) and is expected to reach 79.2% in 2024. Finally, Romanian as a mother tongue is consolidating against a backdrop of greater self-identification with the so-called Moldovan language (the percentage increases from 16.4% in 2004 to 23.3% in 2014 and 32.2% in 2024).

This analysis is relevant to our research because the consolidation process within the Moldovan-Romanian ethno-linguistic community coincides with growing interest in Romania and the EU, leading to greater support for pro-European policies and possible EU accession.

In addition to the surveys and trends indicating a strengthening pro-European orientation in the Republic of Moldova, the outcome of the October 20, 2024 referendum on European Union accession continues to hold relevance, as the results showed a society divided by this issue: 49.6% of the population voted against amending the Constitution, while 50.4% voted to change the Constitution in order to allow the Republic of Moldova to join the European Union.

Alongside the strengthening of the Republic of Moldova's pro-European orientation, we believe that an important Romanian electorate is also consolidating, which supports the development of a strong European Romania that can support the Republic of Moldova's efforts in this process. If this hypothesis is confirmed, then Romanian politicians who promote pro-European policies and a pro-EU discourse would gain greater support than those who promote sovereigntist and anti-EU policies.

Voter participation and preferences in the May 2025 Romanian presidential elections among citizens in the Republic of Moldova

This election campaign was typical in structure, yet notable for its unprecedented mobilization, the presence of "surprise" candidates, record-breaking promotional spending, and a steady stream of scandals (Adevărul, 2025b). The 2024/2025 presidential elections in Romania were also deeply marked by the regional geopolitical context, with strong repercussions on the electoral agenda and public perception. The end of Klaus Iohannis' presidency marked the beginning of an unprecedented presidential race and a reconfiguration of the political landscape. The election campaign cannot be fully understood solely through the lens of Romania's internal dynamics, but rather as part of a broader geopolitical ensemble that includes interconnected actors such as Romania, the Republic of Moldova, the European Union and the Russian Federation. Romania has been placed in the position of "strategic advocate" for the integration of the Republic of Moldova into the EU (Romania Insider, 2024). These

elements of partnership between Romania, the Republic of Moldova and the European Union have increased the relevance of the Romanian presidential election for voters on the left bank of the Prut River.

It is also important to mention the geopolitical security context, which, still determined by Russia's military aggression against Ukraine, has expanded through Russian interference in the elections in the Republic of Moldova (SIS, 2024; Putin, 2025) and Romania (Constitutional Court of Romania, 2024). Economic sanctions and hostile rhetoric have characterized relations with the Russian Federation as tense (European Council, 2025). These realities, which transcend national borders, have significant geopolitical implications.

In the Republic of Moldova, the last few years have been marked by increased political intensity. Elections in Romania brought their own political unrest, through the 2024 presidential elections and the constitutional referendum on EU accession. The Moldovan political scene was marked by political tensions, with "pro-Russian" parties transforming overnight into "Eurosceptic" parties, consolidating the "statist/sovereignist" left wing, and attempting to capitalize on the discontent generated by the energy crisis in the winter of 2023–2024 and the economic crisis caused by rising prices and the impact of inflation. In this context, pro-Romanian public discourse gained visibility. Frequent visits by Romanian leaders and the local media's emphasis on the importance of voting in Romania created emotional mobilization among Moldovans with dual citizenship.

An analysis of voter turnout in Romania has shown a general downward trend in recent decades (Comşa and Tufiş, 2024). This process has been accompanied by moments of significant interest among the diaspora in participating in the electoral process. Amid the ongoing strengthening of Romanian diaspora communities, over the last two decades, the diaspora vote has proved decisive in some elections, particularly as regards the presidential elections. In general, voter turnout among the Romanian electorate has been influenced by socio-economic dynamics, the political and geopolitical reality, European and regional trends, and the aspirations of society, especially among young people (Bădescu, Umbreş, Voicu and Tufiş, 2024). The analysis of Romanian voter turnout in the Republic of Moldova during the May 2025 presidential elections should be considered within the broader context of past electoral participation, both within Romania and across the diaspora. Accordingly, patterns observed in previous years, along with the distinct interest shown in this election, have influenced turnout.

Regarding the mobilization of the electorate in the Republic of Moldova, alongside the distinct dynamics observed in Romania and the Western diaspora, it is essential to consider the established trend of community consolidation around a shared Romanian ethno-linguistic identity. The number of Romanian citizens in this country has increased considerably. This process is accompanied by the expression of preferences for the Republic of Moldova's foreign policy orientation towards closer ties with the EU. Therefore, regardless of the trends expressed by the Romanian electorate in general, the aforementioned factors have led to increased interest in voting among Romanians in the Republic of Moldova. The mobilization of Romanian citizens in the Republic of Moldova has changed over the last two decades, becoming an electoral strategy with real political weight, contributing to the national election result without being its sole determinant. In practical terms, turnout at polling stations in the Republic of Moldova increased from approximately 8,700 voters in the first round of the 2009 presidential elections to approximately 81,000 votes in the 2024 presidential and parliamentary elections (Watchdog, 2025), with 158,143 Romanian citizens turning out to vote in the second round of the May 2025 elections (AEP, 2025).

Table 1. Voter turnout in the 2024 and 2025 elections.

Elections	Votes cast, Republic of Moldova	Votes cast, Chişinău
Presidential elections, first round, November 24, 2024	80,942	36,130
Parliamentary elections, December 1, 2024	81,018	36,829
Presidential elections, first round, May 4, 2025	90,850	42,188
Presidential elections, second round, May 18, 2025	158,143	75,421

Source: author's elaboration based on data from AEP (2025)

A straightforward quantitative analysis of Romanians' voter turnout in the Republic of Moldova highlights a marked rise in engagement with the 2024–2025 electoral cycle. Participation was particularly notable in the 2025 presidential elections, especially during the second round. This heightened involvement was driven both by the distinct profiles of the two candidates and by the perceived impact of the election on key issues relevant to the Republic of Moldova, resulting in a substantial increase in voter turnout. What was at stake extended beyond Romania's future—it encompassed its unique relationship with the Republic of Moldova and the European trajectory of the Moldovan state. All of these issues are viewed in a much broader geopolitical context and against the backdrop of security threats from the Russian Federation and the conflict in Ukraine.

Romanians residing in major urban centers across the Republic of Moldova demonstrated considerable interest. In the absence of data, we can only speculate that this high level of interest was particularly evident among the social, professional and educational elites. A telling example is the very high proportion of voters in Chişinău. This was particularly evident in the second round of the May 2025 elections (47.69%), a sign of greater awareness in the capital (or heightened mobilization resulting from the active engagement of Chişinău authorities in persuading the Romanian electorate of the significance of voting in support of the Republic of Moldova.).

Table 2. Results of the first round of the presidential elections (May 4, 2025).

Candidate	Votes	Vote share (%)
Nicuşor Dan	47,630	52.63
Crin Antonescu	19,630	21.69
George Simion	11,282	12.47
Elena Lasconi	8,686	9.60
Victor Ponta	1,990	2.20
Another candidate/invalid votes	1,632	1.41
Total	90,850	100.00

Source: author's elaboration based on data from AEP (2025)

The vote for the Romanian presidential elections in May 2025 came after a very long and complicated electoral process that began in 2024 and culminated in the cancellation of the second round in December 2024. Numerous debates, the presence of the issue on the public agenda, and the controversy surrounding the success of the nationalist-sovereigntist movement resulted in an electoral participation of over 10% compared to the first round in November 2024. The first round of the 2025 presidential elections revealed a pro-European voting trend, diverging from the traditional pattern observed among the Romanian diaspora in Western Europe.

Candidate Nicușor Dan won the elections in the Republic of Moldova with 47,630 votes, accounting for 52.63% of the valid votes. The remaining votes were dispersed, with nationalist candidate George Simion - who advanced to the second round at the national level and aligned himself with the legacy of the controversial Călin Georgescu - receiving just 11,282 votes, or 12.47%.

The second round, held on May 18, prompted an unprecedented level of voter mobilization in the Republic of Moldova. There was an increase in voter turnout of over 73% compared to the first round. As previously noted, there was a large mobilization in Chișinău.

The results of the second round of the presidential elections showed a very high turnout in the Republic of Moldova in support of Nicușor Dan (who won 88% of the votes) and against George Simion (with only 12% of the votes). Was Nicușor Dan's moderate, liberal, pro-European message persuasive, or did voters primarily reject George Simion's Eurosceptic, sovereigntist rhetoric and his contentious past relations with the Republic of Moldova? It is difficult to say exactly what was the catalyst for these results in the absence of clear research tools, which we did not undertake on this occasion. The overall picture is one of exemplary mobilisation of the Romanian electorate in the Republic of Moldova, reflecting trends observed in the Romanian vote.

The Romanian presidential elections in the Moldovan public sphere

Public perceptions in Moldova regarding the Romanian elections are largely shaped by Romania's image—not only as a neighboring state and member of the EU and NATO, but also as a country linked by shared ethnicity, language, and a common historical and cultural heritage.

If we were to analyze perceptions of Romania's image in the Republic of Moldova, the latest Public Opinion Barometer conducted by the Institute for Public Policy (IPP) (October 2024) shows a predominantly positive perception: almost 82% of respondents consider relations between the Republic of Moldova and Romania to be "very good" or "good" (17.1% and 64.7% respectively). Only about 11% assess them negatively. This distribution confirms that Romania is perceived as a reliable partner and strategic ally, especially in the context of Moldova's European path.

In terms of identity, however, the data suggests a significant division. When asked about a hypothetical referendum on unification, only 35.6% would vote in favor, while 50.2% would oppose it. These figures reveal that, although Romania is valued as a partner, the idea of political unification remains controversial. This discrepancy between the perception of "good relations" and the low level of support for unionism leads us to conclude that Romania's positive image does not directly translate into a pro-unionist orientation. We would like to note that this favorable perception is closely correlated with the pro-European orientation of a significant part of the population, but also with a vivid projection of the Romanian government's policies of consolidated support, especially in recent years.

Against this backdrop, it is essential to understand how the candidates in the Romanian presidential elections are perceived and what kind of political signal they are sending to the citizens of the Republic of Moldova. An examination of the candidates' political profiles and campaign platforms

in the Romanian presidential elections reveals a notably diverse range of ideological orientations and policy positions. The political spectrum is polarized by the presence of anti-establishment candidates with Eurosceptic and sovereigntist views, as opposed to candidates with more traditional views. The campaign was marked by tense public debates, mutual attacks between candidates, but also by the growing role of social media as a strategy for mass communication, targeting and promoting candidates, which led to a climate marked by volatility, deep polarization of the electorate and unpredictability in the election results.

The positioning of the presidential candidates emphasized a wide range of political orientations, going beyond the internal framework of Romanian politics and co-opting populist, Eurosceptic agendas that have spread to several EU states and beyond, touching on some sensitive geopolitical issues for the Republic of Moldova. Understanding these positions is relevant, because it delineates Bucharest's prospective policy direction toward Chișinău, while also uncovering the evolving profile of Romanian voters residing in the Republic of Moldova.

Some candidates built their electoral platform on pragmatism and European continuity. Their discourse emphasized the modernization of institutions, the consolidation of the rule of law and a firm commitment to the European Union and NATO. Regarding the Republic of Moldova, these candidates advocated maintaining Romania's role as Chisinau's main supporter on the path to European integration, without radicalizing their discourse through direct unionist appeals (Radio Europa Liberă Moldova, 2024).

This variety of positions highlighted not only the diversity and ideological pluralism of the Romanian political landscape, but also the fact that the Republic of Moldova is becoming a strategic issue and an important symbolic reference point in Romanian election campaigns. Moldovan voters with Romanian citizenship had to make their voting decision from an electoral offer that ranged from Eurosceptic sovereignty, identity unionism and moderate European pragmatism, each with different visions and impact for the future of Romania-Moldova relations.

Due to the scope limitations of this study, we will present a brief analysis of the nature of relations with the Republic of Moldova, focusing exclusively on the two candidates who advanced to the second round of the 2025 presidential elections (for a more extensive analysis of how the issue of Moldova was addressed by presidential candidates in Romania, see Corpădean, 2025, in this issue).

Nicușor Dan, the winner of the 2025 presidential race, an independent pro-European centrist candidate and former mayor of Bucharest, focused his messages on political efficiency and pragmatism in foreign policy. In relation to Chișinău, he has made public statements in support of European integration and the acceleration of the accession process. He also enjoyed the public support of the Action and Solidarity Party (PAS). In his first speech following the announcement of the election results, he expressed gratitude to the Romanian citizens residing in the Republic of Moldova who took part in the elections, as well as to President Maia Sandu: "Maia Sandu's support was very, very important, and I appreciate the mobilization of the Romanians in the Republic of Moldova." (Pro TV Chișinău 2025).

In contrast, George Simion focused on an identity-based and emotional message centered on the union of the two Romanian states. Although this type of discourse resonated with part of the Moldovan public, it was less aligned with the institutional logic of Brussels, emphasizing the symbolic rather than the pragmatic dimension of bilateral relations. The foreign press describes him as an "uncompromising Trump-supporter nationalist", who has been banned from entering Moldova and Ukraine. He is highly critical of the EU and opposes support for Kyiv in the Russian-Ukrainian war (Politico, 2025). Simion founded the AUR party in 2019. Within a span of six years, this party - initially a fringe anti-vaccination movement during the Covid-19 pandemic - has evolved into Romania's

second-largest political force, drawing support from the working diaspora and younger voters, while leveraging widespread public dissatisfaction with established political figures. A conservative Christian, he supported a failed 2018 referendum to amend Romania's constitution so that same-sex couples could never marry (France24, 2025). George Simion's credibility among voters in the Republic of Moldova has been influenced by his ban from entering Chişinău, but also by his rather controversial and vague messages on security, stating both that he supports Romania's NATO membership and that he contests the support given to Ukraine (Ziarul de gardă, 2025).

Table 3. Republic of Moldova in the platforms of the candidates in the Romanian presidential elections (second round)

Candidate	Moldova's EU integration	Political support/regional security	Unionist identity	Concrete actions/projects
Nicuşor Dan	Very favourable	Bilateral strategic partnership Trilateral partnership Romania – Moldova - Ukraine; Cooperation on resilience	Not a priority issue	Visit to Chişinău; support for the EU negotiation process
George Simion	Ambivalent message	Inconsistent messages; Criticism of regional military support actions	Yes, political objective	Image blockages: ban on entry into Moldova

Source: authors' analysis based on election programs and public statements by candidates.

Candidate George Simion had a negative public image due to his sovereigntist, Eurosceptic and unionist rhetoric regarding relations with the Republic of Moldova. On the other hand, both in the November 2024 and the May 2025 elections, there was a perception of preferences and active involvement of the state leadership in the Romanian presidential campaign (justified by the fact that prominent leaders, led by Maia Sandu, hold Romanian citizenship), favoring certain candidates. In the context of the presidential elections in autumn 2024, even before the second round (which was ultimately cancelled), the Chişinău authorities openly supported Elena Lasconi. During her visit to Bucharest, President Maia Sandu declared her support in a public message: "Dear Romanians, this weekend we are going to the polls again. I will vote for Elena Lasconi because she is authentic and I feel that she loves Romania... I know that Elena Lasconi will not give up her relationship with the Republic of Moldova but will continue what we have started together" (Calea europeană, 2024). There was clear support in the second round of the May 2025 elections for Nicuşor Dan.

Given the large number of Romanian citizens residing in the Republic of Moldova, the topic of the presidential elections in Romania was widely covered in the local media. The most important feature of traditional Romanian elections has been the emphasis on the organizational dimension. Websites such as TV8 and Reality.md have repeatedly published information about the number of polling stations, their locations and the rules for participation. This approach reduces the visibility of the political and programmatic aspects of the elections, turning the electoral process into an administrative matter rather than an intellectual debate.

Some Moldovan media outlets have also focused on the logic of electoral competition. Constant updates on partial results are published by Unimedia and Agora, with an emphasis on the question "what will happen in the second round?". TV8 headlined George Simion and Nicuşor Dan in the decisive elections, then highlighted Dan's performance in the Republic of Moldova. This type of narrative reduced the analysis of the programs and their potential influence on bilateral relations, while reinforcing the perception of the elections as "spectacular competitions" (TV8, 2025).

Pro-Russian publications relied on a geopolitical context, whereas Romanian-language publications refrained from doing so. They emphasized the conflict between the Russian Federation and the West, presenting the Republic of Moldova as an "electoral battleground" for Romanian parties. The vote of Romanian citizens in the Republic of Moldova was thus transformed from a civic act into a component of the geopolitical struggle, which reinforced the feeling that the Moldovan state was vulnerable to regional forces.

The decision of the Romanian Constitutional Court to annul the first round of the December 2024 elections was an event that received special coverage in the media. Agora presented the incident as a democratic crisis, emphasizing its "unprecedented" nature and the unpredictability of the process. Legal and historical explanations were limited, highlighting the perception of institutional instability, even if the facts of the matter cannot be disputed. In the Moldovan public sphere, this could have affected Romania's stable democratic image (Agora, 2024). Analytical publications like Europa Liberă Moldova offered a deeper interpretation, suggesting that Nicușor Dan's victory represents a "positive signal for Chișinău." Their analyses connected the vote to the strengthening of bilateral relations and the continuation of a pro-European direction. By contrast, candidate George Simion was largely portrayed as representing populist risks and possible challenges in relations with the European Union. This portrayal aligns with a subtle, pro-European normative trend. (Europa Liberă, 2025).

A comprehensive analysis of media coverage related to Romania's presidential elections indicates a marked lack of in-depth information. The candidates' electoral programs and public positions were scarcely represented in local media. Although the elections were addressed as a topic of interest, the coverage was largely confined to organizational matters and statistical reporting. While these aspects are undoubtedly relevant, the media offered limited television debates and demonstrated minimal engagement with strategic and political themes.

The significance of the presidential elections in Romania for the Republic of Moldova

The presidential elections in the Republic of Moldova (2024) and Romania (2024/2025) carried significant geopolitical implications. The involvement of the Russian Federation - frequently observed in Moldovan electoral processes - exerted an unprecedented influence on the Romanian context. This issue can be situated within a broader context wherein digital interference has emerged as a pervasive feature of electoral processes across numerous European states. Such interference poses considerable risks and weakens democratic resilience in many countries.

An analysis of the Romanian and Moldovan contexts, both identified as targets of a strategically orchestrated hybrid war underpinned by substantial capital investments, underscores the intricate interconnectivity of social platforms, manipulation strategies, techniques, and tools. These mechanisms can be replicated ad infinitum with clear political consequences at regional level.

The presidential elections in Romania in November 2024 and May 2025 were marked by an atypical campaign, decisively influenced by digital mobilization. Candidate Călin Georgescu, virtually unknown on the traditional political scene, gained massive visibility through TikTok and other platforms, achieving a surprising result in the first round. According to analyses published by Le Monde (2025), this rise was due to an astroturfing campaign, characterized by coordinated networks of fake accounts and influencers paid to artificially amplify the notoriety of a pro-Russian candidate (Le Monde, 2025). As a result of this episode, the Romanian Constitutional Court decided to invalidate the second round of the elections (Romanian Constitutional Court, 2025), an unprecedented decision justified by the risk of external interference. The event raised fundamental questions about Romania's democratic resilience and the ability of its institutions to respond to digital manipulation.

The Republic of Moldova was exposed to major interference in the electoral process from Russia, manifested not only through manipulation and disinformation of public opinion, but also through illegal financing of electoral candidates and a massive campaign to corrupt voters (SIS, 2024), which had a major impact on the integrity of the electoral process (Iașco, Putină, 2025) and democratic resilience. The constitutional referendum in October 2024, which introduced the objective of European integration into the Constitution, was the target of coordinated digital campaigns by pro-Russian networks. According to the NGO Watchdog.md, oligarchs Ilan Șor and Veaceslav Platon financed disinformation campaigns and electoral bribery, estimated at tens of millions of euros, through Telegram and local influencer networks. The main narratives promoted by them are "Moldova is ruled by foreigners", "Moldova is not negotiating on an equal footing with the EU", "The autumn elections will be rigged" and "Russia is the strategic partner of the Republic of Moldova" (Watchdog.md, 2024).

The Information and Security Service of the Republic of Moldova stated that "it has been subjected to a set of hybrid influence actions using organized criminal groups, platforms registered in other jurisdictions, with particularly large budgets provided by the Russian Federation. Citizens of the Republic of Moldova are consciously working in the interests of a foreign state and carrying out actions against the country," according to the presentation of the Report on external interference in Moldova's electoral processes, delivered in a plenary session of Parliament on December 12 (SIS, 2024).

The SIS director warned that Russia's attempts to interfere will continue: "Their strategy - past, present, and continuing into 2025 - has been to infiltrate the political landscape with individuals and entities linked to or under the influence of the Russian Federation, including those covered by the Russian Federation, in order to gain control over Parliament and other institutions in the country. This strategy relies on political and electoral corruption, disinformation and manipulation, as well as street actions and disorder," said the head of the SIS (Europa Liberă România, 2024). The close result of the referendum (just over 50%) showed the direct impact of these campaigns, with the potential to destabilize Moldova's European path. Unlike Romania, where TikTok was the main vector of manipulation, Telegram stood out as the dominant platform for propaganda and mobilization in Moldova.

For Romania and the Republic of Moldova, manipulation techniques included digital astroturfing (artificially amplifying visibility through fake accounts and influencers), thematic disinformation (anti-EU, anti-NATO narratives, religious or cultural conspiracies), transnational mobilization through the diaspora (both in Romania and the Republic of Moldova). These instruments have produced tangible political consequences, including the emergence of anti-establishment candidates, deepening polarization in public discourse, and growing challenges to the legitimacy of democratic institutions.

The cases of Romania and the Republic of Moldova confirm what EU DisinfoLab (2024) called "adaptable influence networks" – flexible digital structures that can be quickly activated in various electoral contexts. In both countries, weak institutions and high levels of news consumption via social media (over 70% in Moldova, according to IPN.md, 2024) have increased vulnerability to manipulation. Thus, the Romanian elections in 2024–2025 and the Moldovan referendum in 2024 should be seen not as isolated events, but as part of a broader network of transnational digital interference. They represent a test of democratic resilience in Eastern Europe, with direct implications for regional security and the European path of the Republic of Moldova.

Conclusions

The organization of the Romanian presidential elections in the Republic of Moldova in May 2025 was directly influenced by the broader context of the electoral process in Romania, the internal situation within the Republic of Moldova, as well as the country's progress toward closer ties with the European Union and the wider geopolitical landscape. Among the key influencing factors were the war in Ukraine and Moldova's relations with the Russian Federation. The electoral issues that captured public attention in the Republic of Moldova included the debate surrounding closer ties with Romania—viewed by part of the electorate as a unionist inclination—alongside topics such as European integration, the war in Ukraine, and relations with the Russian Federation. Additionally, matters related to Moldova's internal political reality, the question of Romanian identity, socio-economic challenges, and Romania's potential role in supporting the Moldovan state generated interest as well. These were among the key dilemmas confronting Moldovan society, contributing to a polarization of the electorate. The serious geopolitical challenges were further complicated by internal dynamics. The Republic of Moldova must consider not only the aspirations of the majority but also the identity divisions that persist within its society.

Analyzing the Romanian community's active engagement in Romania's elections from within the Republic of Moldova highlights a notable case of transnational diaspora participation, shaped by identity, geopolitical, and institutional factors. The exceptionally high voter turnout demonstrated not only a strong sense of civic responsibility among Romanians in Moldova, but also a clear awareness of their role in influencing the shared future of both states. The rise in electoral participation among Romanians residing in the Republic of Moldova stems both from the extension of Romanian citizenship to communities on the right bank of the Prut River and from a heightened awareness of Romania's expanding geopolitical significance in the context of the war in Ukraine and pressure from Russia, as well as the symbolic legitimacy of the Romania-Republic of Moldova partnership in the European accession process. Another dimension of the increased turnout of Romanians in the Republic of Moldova is related to the increasingly categorical assumption of Romanian identity, a process that has taken place in parallel with the increase in the number of Moldovans who have acquired Romanian citizenship. The affirmation of Romanian identity serves both as a driving force behind, and a consequence of, the rise of a substantial segment within the Republic of Moldova's population that supports the country's pro-European direction. This evolution is marked by an increasing interest in Romania and the European Union.

The mobilization of Romanian citizens in the Republic of Moldova, especially those living in large urban areas, has evolved significantly over the last two decades, becoming an electoral strategy with real political weight, influencing the national vote but without determining the outcome on its own. The results of the second round of the presidential elections in the Republic of Moldova showed a very high turnout of voters in support of Nicușor Dan and against George Simion.

Public perceptions in the Republic of Moldova regarding the elections in Romania are largely corroborated with the prevailing view and image of Romania - not only as a neighboring state and a member of the EU and NATO, but also as a country linked through a shared ethnic and linguistic identity, as well as a common historical and cultural heritage.

We believe that the objectives set have been achieved, both through the quantitative assessment of voter turnout and voting behavior during the Romanian presidential elections of May 2025 in the Republic of Moldova, and through the analysis of public perceptions and discourse related to these elections, including the exploration of the significance and influence Moldovan citizens attribute to them. The first hypothesis is confirmed by evidence showing that voter turnout and

electoral preferences were shaped by both the internal political realities and the broader geopolitical context. The second hypothesis is likewise validated. Significance, discourse and public perceptions were largely influenced by political and geopolitical agendas, closely mirroring the points of view promoted by Moldovan media. In summary, the answer to the first research question reveals that the Romanian electorate in the Republic of Moldova has regained and strengthened its electoral engagement. This renewed interest is rooted in socio-economic aspirations, a shared sense of ethnic and linguistic identity, the special relationship between Moldova and Romania, and common pro-European goals. The high voter turnout stands as a clear reflection of this awareness. In the case of the second question, the internal societal and political context, combined with the geopolitical context, influenced the electoral behavior of Romanians in the Republic of Moldova.

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